

Research Article

CHARACTERIZATION OF MORPHOLOGICAL AND FRUITING CHARACTERS OF DIFFERENT VARIETIES IN BER (*Zizyphus mauritiana* L.)

Suraj Kumar* Devsi Karnabhai Varu** and Shankar Lal Kumawat***

*Department of fruit Science, College of Horticulture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh Gujarat

**Principal and Dean, College of Horticulture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh Gujarat

***Department of fruit Science, College of Horticulture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh Gujarat

surajk1757@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The treatment comprises of eight varieties viz., Deshi (V₁), Seb (V₂), Apple (V₃), Umran (V₄), Gola (V₅), Surti Kantha (V₆), Zafrani gol (V₇) and Mehrun (V₈) with Randomized Block Design (RBD). On the basis of morphology, fruit and yield parameters characterization was carried out. Minimum days taken to sprout after heading back was noted in variety Surti Kantha (V₆), maximum shoot length (375.00 cm) in Seb (V₂) and Zafrani gol (V₇). Maximum tree height (4.83 m) was observed in variety Umran (V₄) but the bunching habit was observed in variety Surti Kantha (V₆) and Mehrun (V₈). For flowering minimum days to flowering (80 days) was recorded in variety Gola (V₅) but days to fruit set, maximum fruit set (12 %) were recorded in variety Mehrun (V₈), maximum fruit weight (88.03 g), fruit length (5.23 cm), fruit width (5.63 cm), pulp weight (85.26 g) and pulp: stone ratio (30.77) were noted in variety Apple (V₃). Similarly, minimum stone weight (0.53 g) was recorded in the variety Mehrun (V₈). Highest yield (12.85 kg/plant) and (3559.45 kg/ha) was noted in variety Seb (V₂).

KEYWORDS: Ber, characterization, fruit, morphological parameters, quality, yield.

Citation

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INTRODUCTION

Ber (*Zizyphus mauritiana* L.) is an old and common fruit native to India that belongs to the Rhamnaceae family having chromosome number $2n = 48$. The genus *Zizyphus* has approximately fifty species, 18 to 20 of which are endemic to India [23]; 170 species by [15]. *Zizyphus jujube* and *Zizyphus mauritiana* are the two important species of ber, *Zizyphus mauritiana* is more common in tropical and subtropical regions and *Z. jujube* is found in temperate part of the world. Ber trees are drought resilient because to their deep root structure and nominal water loss via leaf transpiration, making them more suited to dry microclimates [31]. It is an old and popular fruit in India [25] that is enjoyed for its sweet and sour flavour. Ber is a spiny tree or small shrub that grows up to 15-meter-tall and has a trunk diameter of 40 cm or more, a spreading crown, stipular spines, and various drooping branches. The fruits have variety of shapes and sizes. Depending on the variety, it might be oval, obovate, oblong, or round, with a length of 1-2.5 inch (2.5-6.25 cm). Due to cross pollination, jujubes have a broad range of vegetative, leaf, flower, fruit, and quality characteristics. Variation in morphological and physicochemical qualities of ber cultivated varieties should be explored in order to improve this crop. It's a multipurpose plant that's found all over the world in tropical

and subtropical climates [11]. It is more suited to dryland cultivation as a result, it is commonly referred to as a 'desert apple'. Even in the most isolated sub-tropical and tropical locations, it may be cultivated successfully [22].

The largest ber-growing states in India include Rajasthan, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. India positions first among the world's ber growing countries, with an area of 0.5 lakh hectares and a production of 5.13 lakh tonnes. Gujarat is the largest state in India, with 0.118 lakh hectares and 1.20 lakh tonnes produced [5]. From November through March, the fruit is gathered in various sections of the country. After flowering, it takes 150-175 days to reach maturity. Fruits are gathered in South India between October and November, in Gujarat between December and March, in Rajasthan between January and March, and in North India between February and April. Due to the evident that ber is a small crop, there is less varietal study and characterization, varietal popularity in the ber crop is low among farmers. Another big issue with ber is the short crop cycle from flowering to fruit maturity, which means there isn't enough time to investigate a huge variety of varieties and their characteristics. Hard stones and major fruit fly infestation and powdery mildew appear to be the primary obstacles to its widespread cultivation. The obtain ability of a wide variety of variants and their fruiting season, will be used to study distinct features of ber varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An investigation was conducted at Lal Bagh, Fruit Research Station, college of Horticulture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh during the year 2021-22. The treatment comprises of eight varieties viz., Deshi (V₁), Seb (V₂), Apple (V₃), Umran (V₄), Gola (V₅), Surti Kantha (V₆), Zafrani gol (V₇), Mehrun (V₈) with three replications and laid out in Randomized Block design (RBD), 15 years old tree with 6m x 6m spacing. For this studies, twenty-four trees of eight cultivars of ber were randomly selected and placed thrice. The observation was recorded from as per norms of ICAR-CIAH. The growth habit, shoot surface, leaf characters, fruit characters like fruit: apex, shape, surface and stone shape are taken with the visual observation of each replication and treatment. Fruit characters like fruit length and width were with the help of digital vernier calipers and then average was worked out. Fruit, stone, pulp weight and fruit yield were taken through the use of an electronic balance then average was expressed in grams (g). The obtained data was analysed by using the of variance technique for Randomized Block Design (RBD) as described by [21].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The morphological traits of different varieties of ber was noted as per the norms of ICAR-CIAH and which was mentioned in (Table – 1). The semi-erect growth habit was noted in variety Deshi (V₁), Umran (V₄), Mehrun (V₈) and Surti Kantha (V₆). Whereas, variety Seb (V₂), Apple (V₃), Gola (V₅) and Zafrani gol (V₇) were spreading growth pattern among the different varieties. Such types of variability were also recorded by [12], [10] and [19] in ber. The smooth shoot surface was recorded in all variety with the exception of Mehrun (V₈) which was tomentose shoot surface. The results are following the findings of [12] and [30] in ber. From the table, it was concluded that obtuse leaf apex with variety Deshi (V₁), Apple (V₃), Umran (V₄), Surti Kantha (V₆) and Zafrani gol (V₇). Whereas, Seb (V₂), Gola (V₅) and Mehrun (V₈) were acute leaf apex. These findings are in line with [26] and [10] in ber. Cordate leaf base was noted in variety Deshi (V₁), Seb (V₂) and Umran (V₄). Whereas, oblique leaf base in variety Apple (V₃), Gola (V₅) and Zafrani gol (V₇). While, acute leaf base was in variety Surti Kantha (V₆) and round leaf base in Mehrun (V₈). The similar variation was also observed by [26]. As presented in (Table – 1), it revealed that oval leaf shape was observed in variety Deshi (V₁) and Mehrun (V₈), ovate type leaf shape in variety Apple (V₃). Obovate leaf shape was identified in Gola (V₅), Surti Kantha (V₆) and Zafrani gol (V₇). While, cordate leaf shape in variety Seb (V₂) and Umran (V₄). Conformity with the

line investigations observed [10] and [12]. Out of eight varieties, leaf curving character was only presented in variety Seb (V₂) and Mehrun (V₈). Such type of variability was recorded by [12] and [30]. All varieties showed sparsely tomentose pubescence on lower surface of leaf except variety Seb (V₂) which was observed with smooth lower surface of leaf. Such type of variability was recorded by [12]. Alternate curved shape of thorn was noted in all varieties excluding variety Seb (V₂) which was observed with all curved thorns. Such variations in thorn shape was also reported by [20] and [6]. The wide range of variations in morphological characters of leaf and thorn shape was observed this might be due to huge genetic variation in the plant architecture, growth habit and climatic condition.

The data related to morphological characters of plant was represented in the (Table – 2) of different variety. Minimum days taken to sprout (16.33) was recorded in variety Surti Kantha (V₆). However, it was at par with the variety Deshi (V₅) and Mehrun (V₈). While, maximum days taken to sprout (22.33) in variety Gola (V₅). Similar observations were also reported by [32] and [13]. Maximum shoot length (375.00 cm) was noted in Seb (V₂) and Zafrani gol (V₇). However, it was at par with the variety Umran (V₄), Gola (V₅) and Mehrun (V₈). While, lowest shoot length (278.83 cm) was observed in variety Deshi (V₁). The results are in consonance with [18]. Maximum tree height (4.83 m) was observed in variety Umran (V₄). Likewise, minimum tree height (2.57 m) was noted in variety Surti Kantha (V₆). Similar results were also reported by [14] and [29]. The maximum stem girth (21.33 cm) above the pruning height was recorded in Zafrani gol (V₇) but which was at par with the variety Deshi (V₁), Seb (V₂) Apple (V₃) and Mehrun (V₈). Similarly, minimum girth (15.67 cm) in Surti Kantha (V₆). Whereas, the stem girth below the pruning height was noted higher (152.00 cm) in Zafrani gol (V₇) followed by Seb (V₂) as against minimum (30.33) in Apple (V₃). These finding are in line with [8] and [24]. Maximum plant spread NS (4.80 m) was found in variety Zafrani gol (V₇). However, which was at par with variety Deshi (V₁), Apple (V₃), Umran (V₄), Gola (V₅) and Surti Kantha (V₆). While, lowest plant spread NS (3.55 m) in variety Seb (V₂). Whereas, the highest plant spread EW (5.11 m) was recorded in variety Gola (V₅) which was at par with the variety Umran (V₄), Surti Kantha (V₆) and Zafrani gol (V₇). Likewise, minimum plant spread EW (3.22 m) was noted in variety Seb (V₂). The similar variation was also observed by [17] and [8]. The characters related to plant morphology showed the much dissimilarity this might be due to the wide genetic variation among different varieties. In case of flowering characters, bunching habit was only showed by variety Surti Kantha (V₆) and Mehrun (V₈). Minimum days to flowering (80.00 days) was recorded in variety Gola (V₅) which was at par with the variety Seb (V₂), Umran (V₄) and Zafrani gol (V₇). While, maximum days to flowering (103.67 days) was noted in variety Deshi (V₁). This might be due to the heat period are required for flowering is achieved much earlier in variety (V₅) and late in (V₁). These finding are similar to [28]. Significantly minimum days (23.33 days) was recorded to fruit set in the variety Apple (V₃) and Surti Kantha (V₆). However, it was at par with the Umran (V₄) and Mehrun (V₈). Whereas, maximum days (43.33 days) was taken to fruit set in variety Seb (V₂) and Gola (V₅).

This might be due to favorable condition for active photosynthesis activity which lead to translocate the food material in all the direction. These findings are quiet in line with [28]. Maximum fruit set (12.00 %) was recorded in variety Mehrun (V₈) followed by variety Apple (V₃). Likewise, minimum (3.33 %) fruit set was observed in variety Seb (V₂). This might be due to self-incompatibility and sticky nature of pollen. These results are in agreement with these obtained by [16] and [2] in ber.

Table 3: Flowering characteristics of different varieties in ber

Varieties	Bearing habit: Bunching	Days to flowering	Days to fruit set	Fruit set (%)
V ₁ – Deshi	Absent	103.67	41.67	5.00
V ₂ – Seb	Absent	86.00	43.33	3.33
V ₃ – Apple	Present	101.00	23.33	7.67
V ₄ – Umran	Absent	88.00	26.00	3.67
V ₅ – Gola	Absent	80.00	43.33	4.33
V ₆ - Surti katha	Present	100.67	23.33	5.33
V ₇ - Zafrani gol	Present	82.00	41.00	4.67
V ₈ - Mehrun	Present	98.00	24.33	12.00
S.Em.±	-	4.456	2.244	0.375
CD at 5 %	-	13.52	6.81	1.14
CV %	-	8.35	11.67	11.30

The different fruit parameters of eight varieties were also recorded and data mentioned in (Table – 4). From the table, it was concluded that ridged and wart fruit surface was only observed in variety Umran (V₄) and Zafrani gol (V₇). Similar results were also reported earlier by [12]. Round fruit apex was registered in variety Deshi (V₁) and Umran (V₄).

Whereas, flat fruit apex was observed in variety Seb (V₂), Apple (V₃), Gola (V₅) and Mehrun (V₈). While, pointed fruit apex was noted in variety Surti Kantha (V₆) and Zafrani gol (V₇). Oval shape fruit was recorded in variety Deshi (V₁) and Zafrani gol (V₇), round in variety Seb (V₂), Apple (V₃) and Gola (V₅), oblong shape in variety Umran (V₄) and Mehrun (V₈). Whereas, ovate type fruit shape was recorded in Surti Kantha (V₆). This might be due to large genetic variation in the varieties and also due to different growth phase of fruit development. These observations collaborate with the findings of [4], [3] and [27]. The stone, pulp and yield characters of different varieties were presented in (Table – 5). From the table, it was concluded that the oval stone shape was observed in Deshi (V₁), Seb (V₂), Gola (V₅) and Mehrun (V₈), Spindle shape in Apple (V₃), Oblong type reported in variety Umran (V₄) and Falcate type stone shape in Surti Kantha (V₆). Whereas, in variety Zafrani gol (V₇) was observed with club shape stone. Significantly minimum stone weight (0.53 g) was recorded in the variety Mehrun (V₈) which was at par with variety Umran (V₄) and Surti Kantha (V₆). Likewise, maximum stone weight (2.77 g) was recorded in variety Apple (V₃). This might be depending on the fruit shape, weight and genetic variation in the varieties. These results are in agreement with these obtained by [7] and [4]. Significantly maximum pulp weight (85.26 g) and pulp: stone ratio (30.77) were recorded in the Apple (V₃) followed by Seb (V₂). Whereas, minimum pulp weight (6.70 g) was recorded in Mehrun (V₈) and pulp: stone ratio (9.73) was observed in Deshi (V₁). This might be due to the much variation in the fruit weight and its pulp contains and also stone weight. These results were in line with findings of [27] and [1]. For fruit yield, highest yield (12.85 kg/plant) and (3559.45 kg/ha) was recorded in variety Seb (V₂) followed by Gola (V₅). Similarly, lowest yield (2.60 kg/plant) and (720.20 kg/ha) were noted in Surti Kantha (V₆). This might be due the plant canopy structure and more number of new branches leads to more number of the fruit and also due to fruit setting percentage. Such type of variability was recorded by [9] and [32].

CONCLUSION

Wide range of variability exists amongst the eight varieties studied while evaluating for various characteristics *viz.*, tree, leaf, flower, fruit and stone characters. The variety Surti Kantha was found superior in terms of growth parameters like days to sprout, stem girth, tree height, growth habit, leaf characters due to the huge genetic variation in the varieties and its different characters due to the favourable environment for growth and development. The variety Apple was also superior in terms of pulp and fruit parameter. Whereas, variety Gola

and Seb was found superior for high fruiting yield. Superior morphological and fruiting characters helps in the new trait and variety development and further helpful in breeding programs.

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Table 1: Morphological characters of leaf studied as per norms of ICAR-CIAH in ber

Varieties	Growth habit	Shoot surface	Leaf: Apex	Leaf: Base	Leaf: Shape	Leaf: Curving	Leaf: Pubescence on lower surface	Thorn shape
V ₁ – Deshi	Semi-erect	Smooth	Obtuse	Cordate	Oval	Absent	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved
V ₂ – Seb	Spreading	Smooth	Acute	Cordate	Cordate	Present	Smooth	All curved
V ₃ – Apple	Spreading	Smooth	Obtuse	Oblique	Ovate	Absent	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved
V ₄ – Umran	Semi-erect	Smooth	Obtuse	Cordate	Cordate	Absent	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved
V ₅ – Gola	Spreading	Smooth	Acute	Oblique	Obovate	Absent	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved
V ₆ - Surti Kantha	Semi-erect	Smooth	Obtuse	Acute	Obovate	Absent	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved
V ₇ - Zafrani gol	Spreading	Tomentose	Obtuse	Oblique	Obovate	Absent	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved
V ₈ – Mehrun	Semi-erect	Smooth	Acute	Round	Oval	Present	Sparsely tomentose	Alternate curved

Table 2: Morphological characteristic of different ber cultivars

Varieties	Days to sprout shoot after heading back	Shoot length (cm)	Tree height (m)	Stem girth (cm)		Plant spread (m)	
				Above	Below	NS	EW
V ₁ – Deshi	18.00	278.33	4.03	17.33	48.00	4.06	3.64
V ₂ – Seb	21.33	375.00	4.30	20.33	111.33	3.55	3.22
V ₃ – Apple	19.00	293.33	3.83	17.33	30.33	4.15	3.84
V ₄ – Umran	19.33	346.67	4.83	16.67	82.00	4.61	4.10
V ₅ – Gola	22.33	350.00	4.03	16.33	64.33	4.72	5.11
V ₆ - Surti Kantha	16.33	293.33	2.57	15.67	40.33	4.12	4.39
V ₇ - Zafrani gol	20.67	375.00	4.80	21.33	152.00	4.80	4.87
V ₈ – Mehrun	18.00	366.67	4.17	19.33	94.33	3.79	3.79
S.Em.±	0.692	18.213	0.361	1.334	3.259	0.249	0.347
CD at 5 %	2.10	55.25	1.10	4.05	9.89	0.76	1.05
CV %	6.18	9.42	15.37	12.81	7.25	10.22	14.58

Table: 4. Morphological and fruiting characters in different varieties in ber

Varieties	Fruit surface	Fruit apex	Fruit shape	Fruit length (cm)	Fruit width (cm)	Fruit weight (g)
V ₁ – Deshi	Plain	Round	Oval	3.10	2.77	15.03
V ₂ – Seb	Plain	Flat	Round	4.08	4.16	39.27
V ₃ – Apple	Plain	Flat	Round	5.23	5.63	88.03
V ₄ – Umran	Ridged and wart	Round	Oblong	3.34	2.59	10.73
V ₅ – Gola	Plain	Flat	Round	4.14	4.21	39.30
V ₆ - Surti Kantha	Plain	Pointed	Ovate	3.55	2.73	9.30
V ₇ - Zafrani gol	Ridged and wart	Pointed	Oval	3.76	2.63	13.63
V ₈ – Mehrun	Plain	Flat	Oblong	2.53	2.44	7.23
S.Em.±	-	-	-	0.114	0.117	0.817
CD at 5 %	-	-	-	0.28	0.35	2.48
CV %	-	-	-	5.31	5.96	5.09

Table: 5. Stone, pulp and yield characters in different varieties in ber

S. No.	Varieties	Stone shape	Stone weight (g)	Pulp weight (g)	Pulp: Stone ratio	Fruit yield (kg/plant)	Fruit yield (kg/ha)
1.	V ₁ – Deshi	Oval	1.40	13.63	9.73	4.16	1152.32
2.	V ₂ – Seb	Oval	1.33	37.93	28.51	12.85	3559.45
3.	V ₃ – Apple	Spindle	2.77	85.26	30.77	9.16	2537.32
4.	V ₄ – Umran	Oblong	0.73	10.00	13.69	7.73	2141.21
5.	V ₅ – Gola	Oval	2.17	37.13	17.11	10.46	2897.42
6.	V ₆ - Surti Kantha	Falcate	0.73	8.57	11.73	2.60	720.20
7.	V ₇ - Zafrani gol	Club	1.03	12.60	12.23	9.29	2573.33
8.	V ₈ – Mehrun	Oval	0.53	6.70	12.64	6.92	1916.84
	S.Em.±	-	0.112	0.557	1.265	0.678	187.758
	CD at 5 %	-	0.34	1.69	3.84	2.06	569.56
	CV %	-	14.48	3.63	12.61	14.87	14.87

